

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D8.3 – Summary report Stakeholder Forum

WP8 – International Impact, Innovation and Sustainability

Lead Beneficiary: INFRAFRONTIER and EATRIS

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Contractual delivery date: **31 August 2023**

Actual delivery date: **28 August 2023**

H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2

Grant agreement no. 824087

Horizon 2020

Type of action: RIA

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Project Objectives	3
Detailed Report on the Deliverable	3
1. The concept of the life sciences stakeholder forum.....	3
2. Challenges addressed	4
3. Life Science Stakeholder Forum activities	4
4. Conclusions	7
Delivery and Schedule.....	8
Adjustments.....	8

Executive Summary

The Life Science Stakeholder Forum activities in WP8 served to facilitate the alignment of the EOSC-Life policies and outputs with the overall development of the different initiatives within the ‘EOSC ecosystem’. The activities focused on interactions with the EOSC Governance and the EOSC Science Cluster projects. The EOSC-Life coordination team, supported by the WP8 lead, aligned with the other EOSC Science Cluster¹ projects in regular meetings and telephone conferences. This facilitated a coordinated input of the Cluster projects to the activities of the EOSC Executive Board and the associated work groups in the form of several joint position statements, guiding development and implementation of the EOSC Roadmap and the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. WP8 also coordinated or supported the EOSC-Life responses to surveys like the Consultation of the EOSC Executive Board on the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda of the EOSC Association and participated in and contributed to meetings organised by different EOSC initiatives.

Project Objectives

The activities described in this deliverable have achieved the following objectives:

Contribute to the sustainability of the EOSC-Life outputs and the EOSC as a whole by actively participating in the development and implementation of the EOSC Roadmap and the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

Integrate EOSC-Life with the evolving EOSC governance and coordination structures and with the other EOSC Cluster projects.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. The concept of the life sciences stakeholder forum

When the EOSC-Life project began in 2019, it was anticipated that ensuring the global impact and sustainability of the proposed EOSC-Life solutions would necessitate close integration with the emerging EOSC Governance and coordination structures. This integration would involve coordination with the EOSC Cluster projects in different scientific domains to facilitate interoperable solutions and establish connections with relevant global initiatives.

¹ The EOSC Science Cluster projects (for brevity also referred to as “Cluster Projects” or “Clusters” in the document) are ENVRI-FAIR (environmental sciences RI Cluster), EOSC-Life (life sciences RI Cluster), ESCAPE (astronomy and particle physics RI Cluster), PaNOSC (photon and neutron sources RI Cluster) and SSHOC (social sciences and humanities RI Cluster). All RIs in these projects are included in the ESFRI roadmap. We use the term EOSC Science Clusters in this document, since the term “ESFRI Clusters”, which has also been used for these projects (cf footnote 2) also refers to the thematic clustering of ERICs in the ERIC Forum.

To achieve this, WP8 initiated a series of activities under the heading of the Life-Sciences Stakeholder Forum. The aim of this forum was to bring together representatives from biomedical research infrastructures, EOSC Governance initiatives, other EOSC Science Cluster projects. The objective was to develop coordinated strategies and solutions.

A key focus of this initiative was to ensure effective communication, information flow, and collaboration among the EOSC Science Cluster projects. WP8 worked in collaboration with the other Cluster projects to organize regular virtual meetings, enabling frequent updates on project progress. Additionally, they developed aligned policies, strategies, tools, and technologies that contribute to the overall development of EOSC.

2. Challenges addressed

EOSC-Life project is a component of the dynamic and rapidly evolving "EOSC Ecosystem," characterized by numerous initiatives that should ideally align their outputs to maximize potential synergies. Navigating the EOSC ecosystem was complex, particularly in the initial years of EOSC-Life, as various actors and initiatives worked simultaneously to develop the structure of the EOSC.

Considering this, the Life Sciences Stakeholder Forum activities addressed key challenges to ensure that EOSC-Life requirements are integrated into the ongoing development of the EOSC, while also promoting synergy rather than duplication with other initiatives. Another imperative aspect was to facilitate technical cooperation with the other Cluster projects.

With the Life-Sciences Stakeholder Forum, we established a coordination and feedback mechanism to ensure that the advancements within the EOSC-Life project remain connected to the developing overall EOSC governance, activities in other EOSC Clusters Projects, and ongoing open research data initiatives outside of Europe.

3. Life Science Stakeholder Forum activities

3.1. Coordination among the life sciences research infrastructures

Given that not all 13 life sciences research infrastructures are participants in WP8, WP8 served as a contact point and coordination partner to establish common engagement strategies with the EOSC, based on the individual strategies and contributions of each research infrastructure.

This initiative was kicked-off during a meeting on **July 11, 2019**, in Sitges, Spain, attended by representatives from all 13 LS-RIs involved in EOSC-Life. Subsequently, LS-RI directors and coordinators were regularly informed and consulted during EOSC-Life Executive Board Meetings and LSRI Strategy Board Meetings, often held in conjunction with EOSC-Life Executive Board Meetings or at the EOSC-Life Annual General Meetings.

3.2. Coordination with the EOSC Science Cluster projects and the EOSC Governance

Already during their conception, the EOSC Science Cluster projects ENVRI-FAIR (environmental sciences RI Cluster), EOSC-Life (life sciences RI Cluster), ESCAPE (astronomy and particle physics RI Cluster), PanOSC (photon and neutron sources RI Cluster) and SSHOC (social sciences and humanities RI Cluster) had built-in coordination activities to align with the other Cluster projects.

Following the EOSC Concertation Meeting in Brussels on **September 9, 2019**, project coordinators and WP8 lead committed to regular meetings and the development of co-aligned position papers for each Cluster as input to EOSC Governance, particularly the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups.

The "ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC" were subsequently published on Zenodo on **February 19, 2020**².

These papers express the ESFRI RIs' expectations and contributions to the EOSC Executive Board and its Working Groups. They highlight the research community expectations, EOSC's added value to existing research infrastructure, issues requiring attention from the EOSC executive board and the ESFRI RI's commitments to EOSC.

In **2019 and 2020**, WP8 collaborated with LS-RI directors, coordinators, and EOSC-Life coordination to consolidate the EOSC-Life input on the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda of the EOSC Association, as surveyed by the EOSC Executive Board.

During the first EOSC-Life Annual General Meeting in Brussels in **March 2020**, WP8 organized a cross-cluster session on day 2. The panel, titled "Science Clusters and the EOSC: Experiences, common challenges, and possible cooperation," featured the participation of high-level representatives from the EOSC Executive Board (Rupert Lueck), the EOSC Secretariat (Silvana Moscatelli), and the EOSC Science Clusters (Ari Asmi, Rudolf Dimper, Ron Dekker).

In **September 2020**, the Scientific Clusters, alongside the e-Infrastructures, released a concise statement outlining their key positions on the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda: "EOSC - a tool for enabling Open Science in Europe"³.

Starting in **January 2021**, the coordinators of the EOSC Science Clusters engaged in bi-weekly coordination calls, with regular participation from Michael Raess as WP8 lead. These calls facilitated the development of key messages and positions regarding the future progression of the EOSC and the contribution of the Scientific Clusters. Additionally, joint events were organised to foster discussions with EOSC stakeholders. To get a better overview on the status of the different Clusters, each project provided a brief overview presentation during subsequent calls, and Michael Raess presented EOSC-Life on **April 30, 2021**.

In **June 2021** the EOSC Science Clusters published the "Position statement on expectations and long-term commitment in Open Science"⁴. The statement emphasises the Clusters' role in connecting ESFRI and other Research Infrastructures to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The Clusters' impacts include improved access to data, tools, and resources for researchers, creating a cross-border open innovation environment for FAIR data management, and fostering cross-domain interoperability. As

² The term "ESRI cluster projects" in the title refers to the EOSC Science Clusters: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675080>

³ The e-Infrastructures contributing to this paper were EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, and OpenAIRE, see also the links in the publication: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4044010>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4892245>

integral parts of EOSC, Science Clusters contribute to its development and implementation. The position paper emphasises the need for EC support in the long-term role of Science Clusters, enhancing researchers' involvement in Open Science, and suggesting cooperative pathways in the Horizon-Europe framework. It highlights expectations, commitment to EOSC, and provides detailed analyses from each Science Cluster.

The conclusions of the position papers were discussed with stakeholders from the ERIC Forum, EOSC Association, and the European Commission during the "ESFRI Science Clusters' Long Term Commitments to Open Science Workshop" on **June 11, 2021**. The workshop highlighted the significant impacts of the ESFRI Science Clusters' work programs, such as improved access to data, tools, and resources for researchers, leading to innovation in data-driven science. Additionally, they foster a cross-border open innovation environment for FAIR data management and promote synergies, efficiency, and productivity through open-science standards and thematic services. The workshop addressed frequently asked questions about ESFRI Science Clusters and Open Science, covering the state-of-the-art of open science in Europe, Cluster participation in EOSC development, the current role of science Clusters in the EOSC landscape, and future work plans for the Clusters.

In **September 2021** the EOSC Science Clusters summarised their inputs to the EOSC Association for the INFRAEOSC destination in the next RI Work Programme (2023-2024) in a common statement titled "Fostering Open Science with Science Clusters of ESFRI research infrastructures through both community-based and interdisciplinary projects and common actions"⁵.

Prompted by an EOSC Association Webinar on the priorities for the next version of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, the EOSC Science Clusters sent a joint response to the EOSC Association in **October 2021**.

During the 3rd "ESFRI RIs -EOSC Workshop: What does EOSC bring to RI users?" in **January 2022** the specific input of the ESFRI Science Clusters to EOSC was presented. EOSC Science Clusters bridge EOSC and research infrastructures, facilitating RI service reuse and driving new thematic service development. They enhance ESFRI domain alignment and offer value to researchers. Clusters guide new RIs in understanding EOSC's features to avoid redundancy. With their landscape knowledge, they are important contacts for new RIs. EOSC enables interdisciplinary data access, discovery, and cost-effective services, promoting true interdisciplinarity. As a specific use case, the contribution of EOSC-Life to the COVID-19 Data Portal was presented by Niklas Blomberg, the coordinator of EOSC-Life.

In **April 2022** the EOSC-Life coordination with the help of WP8 provided input to the EOSC Association about its major outputs (key exploitable results), the maturity of these outputs and how they will contribute to the development of the EOSC, and the sustainability plans for these outputs.

On **June 16, 2022**, representatives of the EOSC Science Clusters met in Brussels to first discuss among the Clusters common proposals in HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC calls of the Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures Work Programme 2023/2024. This was followed by a meeting with European Commission representatives from DG-RTD and DG-CNECT to exchange on the future role of the EOSC Science Clusters in EOSC and how the European Commission could support that role.

On **July 4, 2022**, representatives of the EOSC Science Clusters and the EOSC Association met online to discuss future interactions and how to structure the Clusters' input to the next iteration of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

⁵ https://www.eosc-life.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/SCLS_infraeosc_HE_Destination_170921.pdf

The EOSC Science Clusters organised a session at EOSC Symposium in Prague titled "Discipline alignment and inter-discipline collaboration: lessons learnt from the Clusters"⁶ on **November 16, 2022**. In this session the Clusters provided an overview of the outcomes of the projects and described converging approaches for user access and Research Data Management solutions and support to user communities, for supporting scientific software, tools, and workflows, for collaborative solutions for training and people development, and generally the role of the ESFRI Science Clusters as key enablers of Open Science.

In **March 2023** the OSCARS proposal was submitted. The OSCARS project unifies the RIs of the ESFRI Science Clusters and relevant scientific communities and has two primary goals: consolidating the accomplishments of the five Cluster projects into enduring interdisciplinary services and practices and spearheading the development of new open-science projects/services to increase researchers' engagement in EOSC.

On **April 3, 2023**, representatives of the EOSC Science Clusters and the EOSC Association met again to discuss how the activities in the OSCARS proposal, if funded, could facilitate the future interactions between the Clusters and the EOSC Association, and the relationship between the EOSC Association ESFRI Working Group.

Already in **mid-July 2022** the EOSC Science Clusters had started the discussion on setting up a common website to broadcast common activities and position papers with links to the individual Clusters' webpages. In **November 2022** the Clusters decided on the final URL⁷. The website concept was further developed and discussed among the Clusters in the first months of 2023 and on **May 19, 2023**, the website went live.

To conclude the Life Sciences Stakeholder Forum activities, at the final Annual General Meeting of EOSC-Life on **June 27, 2023**, a panel discussion titled "What's next for the Clusters" with representatives from the EOSC Association (Ute Gunsenheimer) and the ESFRI Science Clusters ENVRI-FAIR (Andreas Petzold and Anca Hienola), SSHOC (Franciska de Jong), ESCAPE (Giovanni Lamanna) was organised.

4. Conclusions

The Life Science Stakeholder Forum activities in EOSC-Life have significantly contributed to reach the EOSC-Life objectives to actively engage with the developing and evolving governance of EOSC and to not only align the EOSC-Life outputs with the EOSC requirements, but also to provide the input about the requirements and expectations of the life science research communities represented in EOSC-Life towards the EOSC.

Particularly fruitful was the interaction with the other EOSC Science Clusters, which started early in the lifetime of EOSC-Life and evolved into a very stable and productive coordination activity with many important common outputs. The Science Clusters will continue to closely interact and align in the context of the OSCARS project.

⁶ <https://symposium22.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/discipline-alignment-and-inter-discipline-collaboration-lessons-learnt-from-the-clusters/>

⁷ <https://science-clusters.eu>

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes

The delivery is delayed so the results of the last meeting at the EOSC-Life AGM on 28 June 2023 could be included.

Adjustments

Adjustments made: None

